

The Yen Depreciating Equilibrium

Executive Summary

- **The yen continues to show structural vulnerability against major currencies, despite intervention rumors and rate differentials moving in its favor.**
- **The Bank of Japan last moved on December 19th, 2025, raising its key rate to 0.75%, but that failed to generate any relief for the Japanese currency.**
- **The BoJ has limited room to let the real cost of debt rise, and the fiscal risk premium of government debt is primarily being priced into the currency, with inflation breakevens drifting higher.**
- **The yen has entered a depreciating equilibrium, where it has become the valve for risk pricing, and consequent higher import-driven inflation is helping keep real yields low.**
- **While weak domestic demand is preventing inflation from spiraling, the yen will struggle to sustain a rally unless a regime shift materializes, like lower real rates across other developed markets or a credible change in national policy.**

USD/JPY decoupling from interest rate differentials

When inflation came back rampant in the United States and in many other developed markets (DMs), it triggered a global rate repricing, as it forced central banks (CBs) to aggressively hike rates. That produced significant yen weakness, because the Bank of Japan maintained its strong dovish stance and interest rate differentials widened. The correlation between the US and Japan 10-year rate differential and USD/JPY looks particularly strong from 2021 onwards, confirming that rates have been the main driver of the currency pair in recent years. In 2025, the picture has changed, almost mirroring what happened earlier, with inflation remaining relatively high in Japan and cooling in the rest of the world, causing the Fed, the ECB and other major central banks to ease, while the BoJ was forced out of its decade-long policy of negative rates, bringing its key rate to a high of 0.75% at its December 2025 meeting. Rate differentials started to move in favor of the yen, causing the currency to generate a positive return against the dollar in 2025, after 4 years of steep declines. However, since around mid-2025, the Japanese currency has depreciated against the greenback despite differentials moving in its favor, with a striking decline after the BoJ meeting in December. The reason behind this apparently counter-intuitive course of action lies within the structural issues that prevent the BoJ from embarking on an aggressive hiking campaign.

Figure 1: USD/JPY (Black) vs 10-year yield differential (Blue), Source: Bloomberg

Inflation and the Global Rates repricing changed the picture of Japan's monetary and fiscal model

Since the burst of the Heisei bubble in the late 80s, Japan has maintained an ultra-loose monetary and fiscal policy, which brought the government to grow a 240% debt-to-GDP ratio, by far the largest currently recorded across developed markets. The Bank of Japan has historically capped yields through YCC, to both stimulate the economy and sustain expansionary fiscal policy. However, this model can only work without side effects under certain assumptions, like a depressed inflation rate and low real yields across other currencies. Japan was not an outlier prior to 2020. The United States and Europe recorded low inflation figures and rates near zero, making the Japanese model of capped low rates and high fiscal spending seem sustainable, because the opportunity cost of holding the yen was very low, and that allowed the currency to remain stable. The picture has now changed, with inflation exploding across the world, eventually reaching Japan, which has now seen CPI being well above the 2% target since 2022. With higher real rates across other DMs, the opportunity cost of holding yen has risen dramatically, resulting in a strong depreciation. The BoJ has started to gradually raise rates, and JGBs have been under pressure, but all of this has failed to sustain the yen, which after an initial rise in early 2025, keeps looking weak. To gain a better understanding of this conundrum, we must first look at why higher rates usually bring currency appreciation. When a country experiences above-target price increases, the central bank raises nominal rates, and if markets trust their ability to tame inflation and therefore keep real rates positive, inflation expectations remain anchored, no depreciation is priced into exchange rates and expected higher rates lead to currency appreciation. This paradigm of higher inflation, higher real rates and stronger currency, typical of DMs, fails to take place in Japan because the dangerously high debt burden of its government renders restrictive monetary policy unrealistic. The Bank of Japan continues to operate in the JGB market even if CPI runs well above the bank's target, because it cannot risk increasing the cost of public

debt dramatically. Even a modest rise in real interest rates can be politically unsustainable, particularly when the government plans to keep fiscal policy expansionary. This fiscal-dominant model sacrifices the currency in exchange for high fiscal spending. The yen can remain stable only with low global rates, because the ability/willingness of the BoJ to let real rates rise remains weak.

Inflation in Japan: an in-depth look

As previously mentioned, Japan has historically suffered from chronic deflation since the 1990s, due to very weak domestic demand, but in recent years has imported inflation from abroad, and CPI and Core CPI have been above target for almost three years now. The characteristics of the price increases reflect the typical cost-push inflation due to FX pass-through, which was clearly sparked by the yen depreciation of the past few years.

Figure 2: Japan CPI breakdown, Source: Bloomberg

The Japanese economy relies heavily on imports, with core CPI excluding only fresh food, and FX weakness has been directly affecting both core and non-core inflation figures. Food inflation has been the biggest inflation feeder, and also energy has seen spikes, pushing the basket upwards significantly. While service inflation remains somewhat controlled, it is clear that import-led price increases can drag both core and non-core CPI above target in a sustained manner. It is natural to wonder how long wage growth can remain subdued in spite of higher living costs without triggering backlash. While there has been talk about wage hikes, they are still lagging behind CPI, but if that changes, it will only add fuel to the fire by putting pressure on services and housing, which as of right now remain below target.

Japanese Rates Analysis

Despite rate hikes and the nominal long end of the curve moving up, spot real rates struggle to rise due to inflation expectations creeping upwards, with the 10-year inflation breakeven rate rising relentlessly.

Figure 3: 10-year inflation breakeven rate, Source: Bloomberg

Beyond spot rates, we can get a better understanding of the market medium-term rate expectations for Japan by looking at the 5y5y forward rate. The JGB and JGBi markets are illiquid and influenced by central bank intervention, therefore these forward rates are not extremely reliable for absolute values, but having a look at the trend can give us some insight into the recent currency movements.

Figure 4: 5y5y forward rate, built using Bloomberg BVAL Zero Rates

We can see that both the nominal and real rate rose in the first half of 2025, and that is consistent with the yen appreciation that we witnessed, but in the second half of the year they flatlined, specifically the real rate. On the other hand, the breakeven and nominal rate have risen in unison starting in mid-November. Looking at these trends, the course of events appears to be clearer. Medium-term real rate expectations have plateaued halfway through 2025, and basically at that moment the yen started depreciating again. This is a strong signal

that the BoJ is not allowing the real cost of debt to rise, and the fiscal sustainability risk associated with Japanese government debt is being priced into the currency. With the yen depreciating, markets eventually started pricing a higher breakeven, and that pushed up the nominal rate, but the real rate, the real cost of debt remained anchored, despite a brief spike in January 2026. As a result, these rates cannot be considered a true market price, and do not represent the true risk of a country with 240% debt-to-GDP ratio, near zero real growth and strong demographic imbalances. Investors recognize this and treat the exchange rate as the adjustment mechanism. Essentially, we have witnessed a depreciating yen paired with higher nominal yields because the reason of this rise is almost completely due to inflation breakevens, and therefore it cannot be considered real tightening.

The Yen Depreciating Equilibrium

If we consider all these variables, we can conclude that the yen has entered a depreciating equilibrium that started with the initial currency weakness sparked by rate differentials. The yen weakened significantly when the Fed, the ECB and other CBs started their hiking campaigns and real rates rose across the world, while in Japan they remained low, fueling import-led inflation, which is now becoming embedded and is itself putting downward pressure on the currency in what can be described as a vicious cycle. The BoJ has limited room to let the real cost of debt rise, and when rates peak, the yen becomes the valve for risk pricing. Weaker yen leads to more inflation, and that itself puts downward pressure on real rates, and if they remain capped or go lower the currency will weaken further. This reflexive cycle is toxic for the yen, which keeps losing ground also against other key currencies, such as the Yuan, the Australian Dollar and the Euro, and that will keep inflationary pressures consistent moving forward.

Figure 5: CNH/JPY, Source: Bloomberg

What is keeping this equilibrium more or less stable is that inflation is almost completely imported, and while this can be self-sustained, as the course of events has shown, weak domestic demand is preventing it from spiraling out of control. However, there are variables that could accelerate the yen's fall. As previously mentioned, if wage hikes become significant and real wage growth turns positive, stronger demand will boost services inflation, putting even more pressure on the yen and the BoJ. While apparently unlikely, a hypothetical pickup in domestic credit, combined with wage growth, will have even more destabilizing effects, considering the massive amount of excess reserves stacked in the Japanese banking system through decades of relentless bond buying from the central bank. It is difficult to predict what could break this cycle. A few scenarios could involve real yield collapsing across the world, or a credible fiscal tightening policy from the government that will give the BoJ more room to lift real yields. However, Takaichi's government appears to be going in the other direction with fiscal policy, and other DMs seem to have reached normalization of rates after years of QE, rendering the current course of action for the BoJ very tricky. Additionally, more aggressive fiscal policy from the government will do nothing but worsen the situation, because it will not be priced into rates but will depress the currency instead. As long as a credible force that will break this vicious cycle for the yen does not materialize, the Japanese currency will keep experiencing downward pressures. There might be moments of relief, due to dollar weakness and FX intervention, but, as history has shown, they will not solve the problem, therefore it appears reasonable to maintain a bearish stance on the yen going forward.

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